

Electrochemical methoxylation of some benzaldehyde derivatives at platinum electrode

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Abstract : The electrochemical methoxylation of 4-chlorobenzaldehyde, 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde, 4-anisylaldehyde and 4,4-*N,N*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde was carried out at platinum electrode. Constant potential electrolysis was carried out in undivided electrochemical cell. The reaction is an example of nuclear oxidation of aromatic compounds with substitution. The experimental parameters involved in the reaction are discussed here.

Keywords : Electrochemical methoxylation, constant potential electrolysis, substitution, methoxy free radical.

Introduction

Anodic methoxylation of aromatic compounds gives novel addition products of synthetic utility by direct introduction of methoxy groups into aromatic substrates. Electrochemical methoxylation of variety of compounds are discussed in literature¹⁻³ but controlled potential anodic methoxylation⁴ of some common aromatic aldehydes are discussed here first time.

Results and discussion

Anodic methoxylation of 4-chlorobenzaldehyde, 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde, 4-anisylaldehyde and 4,4-*N,N*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde was carried out under controlled potential in methanolic solution containing KOH. After passage of the appropriate amount of electricity, the cell contents were worked up and the products 4-chloro-3-methoxybenzaldehyde, 4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzaldehyde, 3,4-dimethoxybenzaldehyde and 4,4-*N,N*-dimethylamino-3-methoxybenzaldehyde were isolated by column chromatography or by preparative TLC.

We examined the influence exerted on the methoxylation by the temperature, current density, amount of electricity, substrate and electrolyte concentration. The best results were obtained under the following conditions : temperature 25–30 °C, amount of electricity 6.0–8.0 F/mole of the substrate, 3–5% supporting electrolyte concentration. The % yield of the products was 75–95.

Nuclear methoxylation of substrates possessing high oxidation potential is achieved with difficulty^{6,7} whereas easily oxidizable substrates such as 1,4-dimethoxybenzene are transformed to the corresponding quinone bis-acetals by anodic oxidation in high yields^{8,9}.

Inoue *et al.*¹⁰⁻¹⁵ studied the anodic methoxylation of a number of aromatic compounds. They suggested a mechanism involving discharge of methoxide ions at the anode to form neutral radicals which could abstract hydrogen atoms from the substrate. The position of substitution in this free radical reaction is similar to the substitution in chemical reactions. The relative reactivity's of the substrates can be compared with rates of hydrogen atom abstraction from the same compounds in homogeneous reactions.

Researchers^{9,11} have preferred one mechanism involving initial attack on the solvent or supporting electrolyte which is given as :

The position of substitution in this free radical reac-

tion is similar to the substitution in chemical reactions. The relative reactivity's of the substrates can be compared with rates of hydrogen atom abstraction from the same compounds in homogenous reactions.

It has been suggested that the methoxylation process does involve reaction of an electrolytically generated radical with the substrate. This occurs by anodic discharge of methoxide ions to give methoxy radicals.

Experimental

The 4-chlorobenzaldehyde, 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde, 4-anisylaldehyde, 4,4-*N,N'*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde, were purchased from Merck. Mercury, methanol, KCl, KOH were of AnalaR grade.

General procedure for the electrolysis : The reaction mixture prepared by taking 25 mL solution of reactant in methanol and 25 mL 0.1 M aqueous solution of KOH. Controlled potential electrolysis¹⁶⁻²² were carried out in undivided cell (100 mL) made up of glass, equipped with platinum plate as working as well as counter electrode and SCE as reference electrode^{23,24}. A powerful magnetic stirrer was used for proper mixing of the reaction mixture.

All the electrolysis were carried out at their corresponding anodic potential and were completed in 2-3 h. During electrolysis the color of solution becomes dark and current potential data was recorded at an interval of 15 min. The solvent was evaporated and the residue (product) was extracted directly, washed and dried. The observations time interval, applied potential, respective current and the percentage yield of the products recorded in these reactions are depicted in the Table 1.

The products obtained were entirely different from that of the starting material. The products were characterized by microanalysis, ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR and IR. It is obvious from the table that the yield in each case is above 75%. Approximately 8.0 F mol⁻¹ of electricity was passed for the complete electrolysis of the substrate.

Analysis of the products :

The detection of the methoxy group present in the products was done by the Ziesel's method²⁵. As per mechanism following products are formed.

Melting points were measured with open capillary system and are uncorrected. IR spectra in KBr were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 993 IR spectrophotometer. ¹H NMR (300 MHz) and ¹³C NMR (300 MHz) spectra were recorded on a Bruker WM-40C FT spectrometer in CDCl₃ using TMS as internal reference. Chemical shifts are reported in ppm downfield from TMS as internal reference. Microanalysis were carried out in the Elemental Vario EL III.

Spectral studies :

4-Chloro-3-methoxybenzaldehyde (1) : Mol. wt. 170; m.p. 46-48 °C; IR ν_{max} (cm⁻¹) : 680 (Ar-Cl), 695 and 750 (substituted benzene), 1266 (Ar-O), 1684 (C=O), 2815 (O-CH₃), 2856 (aliphatic CH), 3022 (Ar-H); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃/TMS) : δ 3.7 (3H, s, OCH₃), 6.86-7.02 (3H, dd, *J* 2.6 and 5.6 Hz, Ar-H), 9.8 (1H, s, CHO) ppm; ¹³C NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃/TMS) : δ 54.1 (OCH₃), 116.3 (Ar-CH), 123 (Ar-CH), 126.3 (Ar-C),

Table 1. Current potential data as recorded by potential-cum-galvanostat

Time (h)	4-Chloro-benzaldehyde (Current in A)	4-Hydroxy-benzaldehyde (Current in A)	4-Anisylaldehyde (Current in A)	4,4- <i>N,N'</i> -Dimethylamino-benzaldehyde (Current in A)
0.00-0.15	1.00	0.40	0.46	0.39
0.15-0.30	0.96	0.39	0.44	0.37
0.30-0.45	0.93	0.38	0.42	0.36
0.45-1.00	0.89	0.37	0.41	0.35
1.00-1.15	0.87	0.36	0.40	0.34
1.15-1.30	0.84	0.36	0.38	0.32
1.30-1.45	0.82	0.35	0.36	0.32
1.45-2.00	0.80	0.35	0.35	0.31
Applied potential (V)	1.42	1.44	1.30	1.46
Yield (%)	76	85	90	78

130.3 (Ar-CH), 135.7 (Ar-C), 160.7 (Ar-C), 192.4 (CHO) ppm (Found : C, 56.03; H, 4.08; Cl, 20.46. Calcd. for $C_8H_7O_2Cl$: C 56.30, H, 4.10, Cl, 20.82%).

4-Hydroxy-3-methoxybenzaldehyde (2) : Mol. wt. 152, m.p. 81-83 °C; IR ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) : 690 and 760 (substituted benzene), 1050 (phenolic), 1680 (C=O), 2815 (O-CH₃), 2856.5 (aliphatic C-H), 3020 (Ar-H), 3340 (OH); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃/TMS) : δ 3.7 (3H, s, OCH₃), 4.7 (1H, s, OH), 6.86-7.02 (3H, dd, *J* 2.6 and 5.6 Hz, Ar-H), 9.8 (1H, s, CHO) ppm; ¹³C NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃/TMS) : δ 54.3 (OCH₃), 116.9 (Ar-CH), 117.4 (Ar-CH), 123.6 (Ar-CH), 130.4 (Ar-C), 146.5 (Ar-C), 147.8 (Ar-C), 192.4 (CHO) ppm (Found : C, 62.85; H, 5.12. Calcd. for $C_8H_7O_2Cl$: C, 63.15; H, 5.26%).

3,4-Dimethoxybenzaldehyde (3) : Mol. wt. 166; m.p. 42-45 °C; IR ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) : 680 and 755 (substituted benzene), 1680 (C=O), 2820 and 2835 (OCH₃), 2860 (aliphatic CH), 3030 (Ar-H); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃/TMS) : δ 3.26-3.9 (6H, s, OCH₃), 6.86-7.25 (3H, dd, *J* 2.6 and 5.6 Hz, Ar-H), 9.8 (1H, s, CHO) ppm; ¹³C NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃/TMS) : δ 54.2 (OCH₃), 115.7 (Ar-CH), 116.3 (Ar-CH), 130 (Ar-C), 130 (Ar-CH), 146.1 (Ar-C), 151.3 (Ar-C), 192.5 (CHO) ppm (Found : C, 55.62; H, 5.84. Calcd. for $C_8H_7O_2Cl$: C, 56.06; H, 6.02%).

*4,4-*N,N'*-Dimethylamino-3-methoxybenzaldehyde* (4) : Mol. wt. 179; m.p. 72-74 °C; IR ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) : 690 and 765 (substituted benzene), 1675 (C=O), 2820 (O-CH₃),

2855 (aliphatic -CH), 3030 (Ar-H); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃/TMS) : δ 2.35 (6H, s, CH₃), 3.7 (3H, s, OCH₃), 6.70-6.96 (3H, dd, *J* 2.6 and 5.6 Hz, Ar-H), 9.75 (1H, s, CHO) ppm; ¹³C NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃/TMS) : δ 13.7 and 14.2 (methyl), 44 and 54.2 (OCH₃), 116.6 (Ar-CH), 117.7 (Ar-CH), 123.3 (Ar-CH), 128.3 (Ar-C), 139.1 (Ar-C), 148.1 (Ar-C), 192.1 (CHO) ppm (Found : C, 66.65; H, 7.06; N, 7.52. Calcd. for $C_8H_7O_2Cl$: C, 67.03; H, 7.26; N, 7.82%).

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